

Sling Load: System Overview

Position control of suspended loads via aerodynamic thrust for sling load rescue operations

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1. Introduction

The operation of helicopters carrying externally sling loads is a very challenging task for the pilot. This technique is used in several application fields such as logistics, search and rescue or firefighting. Especially during complex rescue operations, there is often a lack of space, and the pilot has to make a great effort to control and stabilize both the helicopter and the load.

As stated by the Swiss air-rescue Rega, it is exceptionally difficult to rescue injured mountaineers from vertical or overhanging rock faces using the longline system. An up to 200-metre long rope is suspended from the helicopter, which enables the rescuer to reach the injured person even in high, steep, vertical rock faces. If the injured person is located under an overhanging rock, the rescuer can pull himself towards the rock by means of a telescopic pole.

Based on the results of previously realized studies on the stabilization and positioning of flying platforms, we now want to propose a novel concept for the positioning of hanging loads, which is suitable for longline rescues. The basic idea is an on-load stabilization and positioning approach. A platform equipped with aerodynamic actuators, environmental sensors like laser scanners or 3D-cameras and IMUs will be mounted at the end of the hoist and must be able to correct displacements and rotations of the load, independently from the positioning of the helicopter. In this way, it is possible to react promptly, not only to foreseeable oscillations, but also to unexpected atmospheric disturbances. This is also a paradigm shift: while previously the hanging load had to follow the helicopter.

2. Project Vision

Two main goals were identified at the beginning of the project: to control the suspended load with high bandwidth and to use sensor fusion to perform control.

Goal 1: High bandwidth control

The goal is to be able to control and position a load, even in mm range. The 'fast controlling' concept is less employed in drone's theory, than 'fast tracking', but its potential in some applications could be remarkable.

The project shows quantitatively results of this control strategy. Sensors were selected, so that they do not influence the performances of the platform, due to resolution, measuring range, data rate issues.

Goal 2: Control based on sensor fusion information

The second goal of the project is to find a combination of sensors, whose information give a precise position information of the platform and allow, through sensor fusion, to give a proper feedback to the control loop.

3. Concept

The system developed is a proof of concept platform, based on the main idea of rescuing people. Precisely, we based our concept on the idea of the rescue basket, as it is possible to see in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Rescue Basket

Figure 2: Concept active stabilizing rescue basket

Above the basket, a platform is needed to fix four couples of contra-rotating propellers, which will be in charge of stabilizing the platform. On the same platform, also IMUs (inertial measurements units) will be placed, in order to be able to control motions and vibrations. This platform is defined as 'Motor platform'. Under the basket, some additional sensors are integrated in the so called 'Sensor Platform'. These sensors can't be mounted on the motor platform, since propellers and other components could interfere and limit their field of view. The platform design can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Platform overview

4. Mechanical design

Four couples of contra-rotating propeller are located in the upper part, the so called 'motor platform'. These are controlled by four 2-axis drives, powered by batteries. On the motor platform, also an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) is mounted.

Some cutouts were performed in order to reduce the weight of the platform. The stiffness of the platform is guaranteed also thanks to vertical connections to the lower platform.

The lower part of the system is called 'sensor platform'. Distance laser measuring sensors, as well as laserscanner and a camera are mounted, with the goal of providing an absolute position of the platform in space.

Figure 4 Platform mechanical design

Some images of the system components:

Figure 5 Details of system components

5. Motors, Propellers and Drives

Motors and propellers of the company T-Motors were selected. An encoder was also integrated in the motor, in order to have a precise velocity and position information.

- Motors: MN5006 KV300
- Propellers: NS 18*6
- Encoder: RLS company
RMB20IC13BC10 + RMM44A3A00
- Drives: Odrives (2-axis controllers)

Odrives are powered by 22.2 V batteries.

Figure 6 Motor, Encoder and Propeller

Figure 7 Odrive

Figure 8 Battery

6. Sensors

Following sensors were considered for the system, to estimate platform absolute position:

	Company / Model	Resolution	Sampling frequency	Pros	Cons
Laser distance Sensors	Baumer OM70	2 μ m	1000 Hz	Very precise High sampling frequency	One-directional field of view, limited between 5 and 250 mm
Laserscanner	RPLidar A2M8	5 cm	10 Hz	Can see obstacles up to 8 m distance.	Resolution and sampling frequency too low to ensure stiff control 360° scanning, but only 2D, i.e. at laserscanner height.
Pixy Camera	Pixy 2	< 1 cm	60 Hz	Sampling frequency good for system stability (limit). Acceptable precision.	Colored markers needed to perform position estimation. Light influence.

The resulting absolute position was combined with the information from the IMU unit SBG Ellipse-A. This sensor provides 3-axis accelerations, gyro angular velocity and Euler angles at a sampling rate of 200 Hz.

Figure 9 Baumer OM70

Figure 10 RPLidar A2M8

Figure 11 PixyCam 2

Figure 12 SBG Ellipse-A

Test results showed how the resolution of the laserscanner and the low sampling frequency were too low to ensure system stability and control capabilities. With Pixy cam it was possible to get a stable system, but low positioning precision, while with Baumer laser sensors a very high positioning precision was reached, with a stable system, was reached. Further details will be discussed in section “Control Strategies”.

7. Electrical connections

Figure 13 Electrical connections

8. Control Strategies

Platform position control was tested with three different sensors, capable of providing an absolute position of the system: laser distance sensors, laserscanner and a pixy camera.

8.1 Position control with Baumer Laser Distance Sensors

Laser distance sensors have a high resolution and sampling frequency. This allowed to demonstrate the stiffness of the positioning control of the platform, with no influence from the measuring source.

This solution gave very good results, a stable system and a positioning precision under 2 mm.

Figure 14 Control system with Baumer sensors

Figure 15 Test results with Baumer sensors

Figure 16 XY Test results with Baumer sensors

8.2 Position control with Laserscanner

As an alternative, a laserscanner was used. This sensor can detect objects up to 8 m distance, but is less precise than the previous used sensors. This led to a positioning error around 5 cm. Additionally, data are available with a frequency of 10 Hz. All these factors led to an unstable system and so also the impossibility to use this sensor for positioning purposes.

Figure 17 Control System with laserscanner

Figure 18 Test results with laserscanner

8.3 Position control with Pixy Camera 2

The last test was performed using a Pixy Cam 2, which had to detect four red markers, lying on the floor, under the platform. Position and orientation are determined by the position of those markers on the camera picture. This solution led to a stable system, not as stiff as the first solution, with laser distance sensors, but anyway with a positioning precision under 1 cm.

Figure 19 Control system with PixyCam

Figure 20 Test results with PixyCam

9. Conclusions

During the project, a platform was realized, which was capable of performing stabilization and positioning tasks in three degrees of freedom (displacement in x-y direction, rotation around z-axis). Positioning precision varied, depending on different sensors configuration. Also sampling rate of sensor signals played a very important role on system stability.

Additionally, some unexpected hardware limitations on the drives limited the maximum allowed speed for the motors and therefore also the performances and stiffness of the control loop. Within this project, it was possible to gather important knowledge about available components, system dynamics and behavior, depending on different configuration and control strategies.

This ensures a good basis for further development of the system and related stabilization and positioning concepts.